

SCIENCE TEACHERS AS DESIGN THINKERS: THE CASE OF PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL LEARNING RESOURCE WRITERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the integration of design thinking in the creation of science learning resources in public high schools, emphasizing a user-centric approach for innovative solutions to educational challenges. Through qualitative research, including interviews with science learning resource creators, the study identifies the processes, opportunities, and challenges of implementing design thinking. Findings suggest that design thinking fosters creativity, empathy, and an iterative process, enhancing the quality of science instruction and promoting 21st-century skills among students. However, challenges such as a lack of a well-articulated pedagogical framework and the need for teacher training in design thinking principles persist. The research contributes to educational discourse by offering insights into effective design-thinking applications and developing a design-thinking-based learning module as a practical tool for educators. This study holds significance for science learning resource writers, educators, policymakers, and students, highlighting the transformative potential of design thinking in science education amidst evolving educational landscapes.

Keywords: *21st-century skills, design thinking, educational challenges, educational policy, empathy in education, innovative solutions, iterative process, learning resources, pedagogical framework, science education, stakeholder feedback, teacher training, user-centric approach*

INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, the scholarly interest in Design Thinking has notably increased, with the Web of Knowledge database now listing over 180 articles on the subject (Fleury, 2016). Initially rooted in the practices of engineers and designers, Design Thinking has evolved into a critical educational focus (Hynes, 2012; Koh & Chai, 2016; Blundell, 2022). Its appeal lies in its user-centric approach, prioritizing the needs and viewpoints of individuals to foster innovative solutions for complex global issues (Razzouk & Shute, 2012; Fleury et al., 2016; Yurkofsky et al., 2020; Blundell, 2022). This emphasis on understanding and addressing user needs has broadened its application beyond traditional fields (Sun, Wang, & Hu, 2023).

For educators, design thinking emerges as a conduit for ceaseless professional enhancement (Henriksen, Richardson, & Mehta, 2017; Kyza & Nicolaidou, 2017; Noh & Karim, 2021; DeLuca et al., 2015; Koh, Chai & Lim, 2017; Lor, 2018; Arrington & Willox, 2021; Chai, 2018, 2021; Chiu et al., 2021; Blundell, 2022). This method posits that a medley of astute observation, empathy, brainstorming, and prototyping can beget innovative ideas finely tuned to both the contextual nuance and broader educational sphere (Aksela, M. 2019; Andino, C.I., 2017; Yurkofsky et al., 2020; Blundell, 2022).

A surplus of models and versions of design thinking has been intertwined into the broader scope of educational research (McFadden & Roehrig, 2017; Kelly, N., et al., 2019; English, Adams & King, 2020; Spoon et al., 2020; Yeh, Chan, & Hsu, 2021; Kim, 2021; Georgiev, 2012). Proponents argue that the approach leverages the inherent dynamic and complex relational facets of educational settings, thereby enabling educators to engage in sustained self-betterment (Chai, 2018; Stevenson et al., 2019; Yeh et al., 2021; Tualaulelei & Halse, 2021; Noh & Karim, 2021; Blundell, 2022). Nonetheless, design thinking still lacks a well-articulated pedagogical framework (Spoon, 2020).

This study sheds light on science learning resource creators in public high schools, a group that has been overlooked thus far. The aim is to contribute meaningful insights to the conversation on design thinking in pedagogical circles. The results of this study could provide valuable insights into how design thinking can be more effectively incorporated into the creation of learning resources, enhancing science instruction and promoting the development of 21st-century skills among students. Moreover, the resulting design-thinking-based learning module could be a practical tool for other educators aiming to integrate design thinking into their work.

Research Questions

This study focuses on science teachers who make learning materials in public high schools. This research looks at how these teachers can use design thinking, a way of solving problems by really understanding what people need, to improve what they are doing. With that said, the main goals for this study are as follows:

1. Describe the design thinking processes of science learning resource writers,

2. Identify the opportunities and challenges they encounter in implementing design thinking, and
3. Develop a learning module informed by the principles of design thinking.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The qualitative methodology underpinning this study is designed to gain a deep understanding of the complex nature of design thinking as it applies to science learning resource creation. This approach, suited for exploring rich, detailed insights into the participants' interpretations and interactions within their social contexts (Creswell, 2007), is interpretative and centered on the phenomenon it seeks to understand (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Qualitative research design is particularly adept at exploring "how" or "what" questions (Creswell, 2007), allowing for a broad, in-depth exploration into how design thinking is operationalized by science learning resource writers and how this impacts both pedagogical approaches and learning outcomes.

This study employs a qualitative design that does not seek to generalize findings but to provide a detailed understanding of a central phenomenon within a bounded context. As such, it aligns with the tradition of qualitative case studies, which prioritize the depth of understanding over breadth and are tailored to investigate the nuances and complexities of a specific instance or setting (Creswell, 2007). The chosen design facilitates an exploration into the lived experiences, challenges, and successes of individuals deeply engaged with design thinking in the creation of learning resources. By delving into these experiences, the study aims to uncover the intricacies of design thinking as it intersects with educational practices within the Junior High School science context.

Research Locale

The Department of Education's Schools Division Office (DepEd SDO) in Quezon Province serves as a critical component of the local education system, dedicated to upholding and improving the standards of pedagogy and student learning. The researcher chose this division as the setting for the study due to its notable cadre of skilled learning resource writers who play a crucial role in developing educational content. The researcher's location within the same province further influenced the choice, facilitating an immersive and thorough comprehension of the division's operations. These writers form an integral part of the research. Their significant contributions and experiences provide valuable insights into the educational landscape, thus enhancing the depth and quality of the study overall.

Population and Sampling

The study follows a case study strategy of inquiry, which typically involves an in-depth exploration of a central phenomenon within a bounded system or with a defined set of participants (Creswell, 2007). In this study, a purposive sampling strategy was

employed to select a focused group of participants who are uniquely positioned to provide in-depth insights into the use of design thinking in the creation of science learning resources. Five experienced science teachers and learning resource writers from the Schools Division Office in Quezon Province were chosen due to their extensive involvement in curriculum development and their practical experience with innovative educational strategies.

The choice to include only five participants aligns with the qualitative case study's emphasis on depth over breadth. Creswell (2007) suggests that qualitative research should include language that delimits the scope of participation, helping to define the parameters of the research study. In this case, the limitation to five participants allows for a comprehensive exploration of each participant's unique contributions and experiences as both science teachers and learning resource writers. This focused approach facilitates a detailed and nuanced understanding of the central phenomenon—design thinking in learning module development—within the specific context of Junior High School science education.

The selected participants represent a diverse range of experiences and backgrounds in science education. Each participant brings a unique perspective to the study, having been involved in various capacities ranging from classroom teaching to the development of educational resources. Their experiences are particularly relevant as they align closely with the study's aim to explore the application and impact of design thinking in educational resource development. The participants' direct involvement in these areas provides valuable practical insights, making their contributions critical to the depth and richness of the study. The choice of five participants is based on the qualitative nature of the study, where depth rather than breadth is prioritized. This number allows for comprehensive and detailed data collection from each participant, ensuring that the study can delve deeply into individual experiences and perspectives while remaining manageable and focused. The small sample size is conducive to a detailed thematic analysis, allowing for a thorough exploration of complex themes and nuances in the data.

It is acknowledged that the small sample size and the specific context of the study may limit the generalizability of the findings. However, the depth and richness of the data gathered from this purposive sample offer significant insights into the topic. Future research could expand on these findings by including a broader and more varied sample, potentially enhancing the generalizability of the results.

The sampling strategy is directly aligned with the research questions of the study. By focusing on participants who are actively engaged in both teaching and resource development, the study ensures that the data collected is directly relevant to understanding how design thinking is operationalized in the development of science learning resources and its potential impact on teaching and learning.

Instrumentation

The Interview Guide Questionnaire for Learning Resource Writers was developed and utilized by the researcher as part of the data collection process in this study. The researcher carefully designed this tool to align with the study's objectives. It aims to elicit

detailed responses on design thinking process, challenges, opportunities, and developing a learning module within the context of science learning resource creation. As a self-designed instrument, it allows the researcher to tailor the questions to the specific research context, thereby enhancing the relevance and depth of the data collected. This semi-structured questionnaire provides a framework for conducting the interviews while allowing participants to share their thoughts and experiences beyond the provided prompts, ensuring nuanced understanding of the research topic. Being the interviewer, the researcher can also clarify any uncertainties during the interview, allowing for more accurate and comprehensive data.

For Objective 1: Describe science learning resource writers' design thinking. The researcher designed questions 1.1 and 1.2 to probe into the participants' creative processes when they develop new learning resources. It includes how they identify student needs, iterate and refine their ideas, and handle changes or revisions. The answers to these questions will provide insights into their design thinking process and practices.

Under Objective 2: Elicit opportunities and challenges for science learning resource writers in design thinking, questions 2.1 and 2.2 explore the participants' experiences with the obstacles and advantages they encounter when applying design thinking in their work. Their responses will reveal the challenges they face, the opportunities they recognize, and their suggestions for improving the process of creating learning resources.

Finally, to address Objective 3: Develop a learning module following the design thinking process, the researcher formulated questions 3.1 and 3.2 to seek the participants' insights on the essential elements, techniques, or methods to include in a training module on resource creation. Their responses will be crucial in developing a learning module that is grounded in the real-world experiences of science learning resource writers.

To ensure reliability and validity of the instrument, it underwent a comprehensive validation process. The questionnaire was reviewed and validated by a panel of experts consisting of three Science Master Teachers, recognized for their extensive experience and expertise in the field of science education. Additionally, a Master Teacher specializing in Applied Linguistics evaluated the instrument to ensure the clarity, appropriateness, and linguistic precision of the questions. Furthermore, a Teacher-III, who is also a Registered Guidance Counselor, reviewed questionnaire. This inclusion added a valuable perspective on the instrument's ability to effectively capture the psychological and behavioral aspects relevant to the study. Their collective insights and feedback were instrumental in refining questionnaire, ensuring that it is robust, comprehensive, and aligned with the study's goals.

Based on the feedback received from these experts, revisions were made to the questionnaire to enhance its clarity, relevance, and effectiveness. The final version of the instrument thus represented well-considered balance between scientific rigor and practical applicability, tailored to capture the nuanced complexities of the research topic.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon obtaining the approval of the research adviser, the researcher initiated the data-gathering procedure, which was rooted in ethical research practices. The process began with the researcher securing signed consent forms from the participants, who were identified through purposive sampling. The sample consisted of five learning resource writers from the DepEd Schools Division Office in Quezon, chosen for their relevant experience and expertise in science education and resource development.

The researcher conducted interviews online to accommodate convenience and accessibility for all participants while ensuring a conducive environment for open and detailed discussion. The semi-structured interview guide served as a roadmap during these interactions, promoting a focused yet flexible exploration of the study's objectives. With the participants' consent, all interviews were recorded to maintain the integrity and authenticity of the data.

After completing interviews, the researcher diligently transcribed the recordings, paying attention to capturing the nuances of the responses. While meticulous and time-consuming, this task ensured that the data was accurately documented for the next stage of the research process - data analysis. Through these steps, the researcher gathered rich, qualitative data necessary for the study while upholding the principles of research ethics and participant confidentiality.

Adhering to the highest ethical standards was paramount in this research, guided by the principles outlined in the American Psychological Association's Publication Manual (2019). Central to our approach was informed consent, ensuring that all participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights as participants. Participation was voluntary, with participants informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained, with all identifiable information anonymized in the study's findings and data securely stored, accessible only to the research team. Moreover, the well-being and comfort of participants were prioritized throughout the research process, particularly during the data collection phase. This ethical framework not only safeguarded the participants but also reinforced the integrity and credibility of the research findings.

Data Analysis

In line with that of Creswell's recommendations for qualitative research, this study employed NVivo, a specialized software that supports the systematic qualitative data evaluation and interpretation (Creswell, 2007). Following the thematic analysis framework outlined by Braun & Clarke (2006), the study utilized NVivo to organize, code, and map out concepts, thereby facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the collected data.

At the outset, all interview transcriptions were imported into NVivo. This initial step allowed for an organized review of the data, enabling the researcher to become intimately familiar with the depth and breadth of the content. Creswell highlights the importance of such systematic organization of data in qualitative research, and NVivo provided the necessary tools for this phase of analysis (Creswell, 2007).

The generation of initial codes was then conducted within NVivo, allowing the researcher to tag meaningful sections of text systematically. Creswell notes that software like NVivo is crucial for coding, retrieving, building theories, and conducting analyses of the data in a qualitative study (Creswell, 2007). This coding process within NVivo aided in preliminary themes identification that captured intricacies of participants' experiences.

NVivo's advanced analysis capabilities were leveraged to refine these themes, ensuring they accurately represented participants' perspectives. This aligns with Creswell's (2007) approach to qualitative data analysis, where the researcher iteratively revisits and refines the data to ensure the themes' robustness and relevance.

The final stage of the analysis involved using NVivo to define and name the themes, with the software's modeling features helping to establish connections between them. The result was a set of clearly articulated themes that were both representative of the data and reflective of the central phenomenon under study.

To conclude the analysis, NVivo's reporting features were used to extract, summarize, and present the data findings. These findings, rich with detailed descriptions and direct quotations from participants, were synthesized into the final report, providing an insightful narrative of the experiences of science learning resource writers engaged in design thinking. This thematic analysis, enhanced using NVivo and informed by Creswell's methodological guidance, offered a nuanced understanding of qualitative data, illuminating the complex dynamics at play in the context of the study.

RESULTS

Table 1: Design Process of Science Learning Resource

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
1.1 Can you describe the process you typically follow when creating a new science learning resource?	<i>P1: "I start by thinking about the learning goals and understanding the learner's needs..."</i>	Understanding Learner's Needs, Learning Goals Orientation
	<i>P2: "Brainstorming is the first step, then I do research on how to make the topic interesting..."</i>	Brainstorming, Research, Making Learning Engaging
	<i>P3: "I start with identifying the key concepts, then designing activities..."</i>	Key Concepts Identification, Activity Design
	<i>P4: "I begin by identifying the specific learning objectives for the topic..."</i>	Learning Objectives Focus

	<i>P5: "I consider first the Most Essential Learning Competency (MELC)..."</i>	Importance of Learning Competencies
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Table 2: Dealing with Changes or Revisions

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
1.2 How do you deal with changes or revisions during the development of your resources?	<i>P1: "I try to be open to feedback and understand where it is coming from..."</i>	Openness to Feedback
	<i>P2: "I usually get a lot of feedback, which I use to make changes..."</i>	Use of Feedback for Revisions
	<i>P3: "Revisions are inevitable. I ensure I have a systematic process for addressing them..."</i>	Systematic Revision Process
	<i>P4: "I'm very systematic when it comes to revisions. I divide the whole content into smaller parts..."</i>	Partitioned Approach to Revisions
	<i>P5: "I revise the module by part from beginning to end..."</i>	Strategic Revision Process

Table 3: Challenges in Resource Creation

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
2.1 What are the main challenges you face when trying to innovate in your resource creation?	<i>P1: "Sometimes the curriculum can be a limitation..."</i>	Curriculum Limitations
	<i>P2: "The biggest challenge is to make the resources interesting and engaging..."</i>	Engaging Resource Creation Challenge
	<i>P3: "One of the main challenges is incorporating technology..."</i>	Incorporation of Technology
	<i>P4: "The challenge lies in designing learning resources that align with both the learning objectives and students' needs..."</i>	Aligning Learning Objectives and Students' Needs
	<i>P5: "The main challenge I encounter during my resource creation was</i>	Home-based Learning Challenge

	<i>formulating activities for the lesson that is applicable at home setting..."</i>	
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Table 4: Opportunities and Benefits in Design Thinking

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
2.2 Can you share any opportunities or benefits you've experienced when applying design thinking in your work?	<i>P1: "Design thinking allows for greater creativity and innovation..."</i>	Greater Creativity, Innovation
	<i>P2: "Design thinking helps me to put myself in the student's shoes..."</i>	Empathy, Student-centric Approach
	<i>P3: "Applying design thinking allows me to explore multiple possibilities..."</i>	Exploration of Possibilities
	<i>P4: "I've been able to create more personalized and effective learning resources..."</i>	Personalized and Effective Learning Resources
	<i>P5: "By applying design thinking, you are able to test your ideas and enables to generate more ideas beneficial to the learning process..."</i>	Idea Testing, Generation of Beneficial Ideas

Table 5: Key Elements in Resource Creation Training

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
3.1 If you were to train other science teachers on resource creation, what key elements or steps would you include in that training?	<i>P1: "Understanding the students, brainstorming ideas, creating a draft, testing the resource, and making revisions..."</i>	Understanding Students, Brainstorming, Testing, Revisions
	<i>P2: "Identifying learning objectives, doing research, creating a detailed plan..."</i>	Learning Objectives Identification, Research, Planning
	<i>P3: "The training should cover learning theory, understanding the learners' needs..."</i>	Learning Theory, Understanding Learners' Needs
	<i>P4: "The key elements I would focus on are needs assessment, understanding the curriculum..."</i>	Needs Assessment, Understanding the Curriculum

	<i>P5: "Brainstorming, Look for Reliable Resources, Planning Stage, Formulating modules with Higher Order Thinking Skills Questions..."</i>	Brainstorming, Resource Reliability, Planning, Higher Order Thinking Skills
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Table 6: Techniques or Methods for Resource Creation

Question	Excerpt from Response	Themes
3.2 Can you suggest any specific techniques or methods that should be part of a learning module on resource creation?	<i>P1: "Use of visual aids, simulations, and interactive elements..."</i>	Visual Aids, Simulations, Interactivity
	<i>P2: "Interactive activities, assessments, use of multimedia..."</i>	Interactive Activities, Assessments, Multimedia Use
	<i>P3: "The learning module should include active learning strategies..."</i>	Active Learning Strategies
	<i>P4: "Methods like problem-based learning, case studies, and project-based learning..."</i>	Problem-based Learning, Case Studies, Project-based Learning
	<i>P5: "With the use of different activities and assessments, the students will have a deepening of their understanding..."</i>	Variety of Activities, Assessments, Deep Understanding

DISCUSSION

Table1

Participant 1's approach to prioritizing learning goals and understanding learners' needs is pivotal to the design thinking process in education, reflecting a user-centered approach that aligns with principles outlined by Brown (2009). This is supported by recent findings suggesting that understanding the student perspective is a critical aspect of successful learning resource creation (Auditor & Mutya, 2022).

The brainstorming and research stages emphasized by Participant 2 are in line with the iterative nature of design thinking, where multiple ideas are generated and explored. This approach to making learning engaging is crucial, especially in the digital era where student engagement is a significant challenge (Lake et al., 2021).

Participant 3's method of identifying key concepts and designing activities resonates with the principles of active learning, a core component of design thinking in

education. The focus on activity design underscores the necessity of interactive and engaging educational materials (Lake et al., 2021).

Participant 4's focus on identifying specific learning objectives echoes the need for aligning educational resources with desired outcomes, a principle supported by the design thinking approach (Auditor & Mutya, 2022). This focus on learning objectives ensures that the resources are purposeful and meet educational standards.

The emphasis on learning competencies by Participant 5 aligns with the broader educational trend towards competency-based learning, a fundamental aspect of design thinking education, preparing students for complex real-world challenges (Lake et al., 2021).

The processes described by the participants illustrate a strong alignment with the principles of design thinking in education, wherein understanding the user, iterating on ideas, and creating engaging, competency-focused resources are paramount. This approach not only serves immediate educational needs but also prepares students for future challenges, thereby fulfilling education's dual role as a means of knowledge dissemination and a platform for skill development.

Table 2

Participant 1's embrace of feedback is a symbol of the creative and iterative process outlined by both previous discussion and the design thinking framework. This openness to feedback is a critical mechanism for *improvement*, reflecting the pedagogical commitment to fostering creativity and personalization in education (Barber et al., 2013; Liedtka & Ogilvie, 2011).

Participant 2's application of feedback for making changes is aligned with the responsive and adaptive approach advocated by Christensen et al. (2008), and the principle of iteration that lies at the heart of both design thinking and the active engagement of learners (Dam & Siang, 2020).

Participant 3's systematic revision process, Participant 4's partitioned approach to revisions, and Participant 5's end-to-end strategic revision process collectively embody the methodical, detail-oriented quality assurance and adaptability necessary for modern educational resource development. These methods reflect the iterative principles of design thinking and constructivist perspective, ensuring that learning resources remain relevant and responsive to the dynamic educational landscape (Carlgren, Rauth, & Elmquist, 2016; Luchs, Swan, & Griffin, 2016; Beckman & Barry, 2007).

Table 2 highlights the participants' dedication to quality and innovation in resource development. Their strategies are informed by both the principles of design thinking and the constructivist approach to education, demonstrating a commitment to continuous improvement, learner engagement, and preparation of students for a globalized and technologically advanced world. The integration of feedback, active learner involvement, and an iterative, non-linear approach to resource creation encapsulates the dynamism required in today's educational landscape, as participants act as "creative creators" within evolving framework of 21st-century skills and innovation (ACTRC, 2015; Serrat, 2010).

Table 3

Participant 1 finds curriculum limitations a significant barrier to innovation. The strictness and prescriptive nature of many curricular structures can impede incorporation of novel teaching methods and content, necessitating a balance between adhering to educational standards and embracing pedagogical innovation. Such constraints require educators to seek flexible and creative solutions to foster meaningful learning experiences, highlighting the need for curricular reform to accommodate contemporary educational demands (Schneider & Preckel, 2017; UNESCO, 2021).

Participant 2 stressed that creating resources engaging and interesting remains a central challenge, particularly in an era filled with digital distractions. Engaging students requires innovative educational resources that leverage both pedagogical insights and technological advancements. Research underscores the crucial role of digital innovation in transforming education by enhancing the quality and relevance of learning and improving educational governance (Herrington, Reeves, & Oliver, 2010; UNESCO, 2024).

For Participant 3, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted both opportunities and challenges in incorporating technology into educational settings. Educators have had to rapidly adapt to using various technologies, often without prior training, emphasizing the need for ongoing professional development in technological pedagogy. This adaptation underscores broader challenge of integrating technology in a way that enhances learning without overshadowing educational content (Bond et al., 2021; Kirkwood & Price, 2014).

Participant 4 said aligning learning objectives with students' needs is essential for successful educational innovation. This challenge involves designing resources that not only adhere to curricular goals but also cater to diverse student profiles and learning preferences. The alignment ensures that educational innovations are both pedagogically sound and personally relevant to students, highlighting the need for personalized education (Darling-Hammond, Zieleski, & Goldman, 2014; UNESCO, 2021).

Lastly, Participant 5 shared that rapid shift to home-based learning has introduced new challenges in educational resource development. Educators have had to innovate to create resources suitable for at-home learning, which requires considering the unique contexts and constraints of the home environments. This shift underscores the growing importance of flexibility in educational resource creation to support remote learning (Bond et al., 2021; Trust & Whalen, 2020).

Table 4

Participant 1's experience that design thinking fosters greater creativity and innovation is supported by recent literature, which underscores the method's potential to unlock creative potential and drive innovative solutions in educational settings. Design thinking's iterative process, with its emphasis on ideation and prototyping, encourages educators to develop novel approaches to teaching and learning.

The emphasis on empathy and a student-centric approach, as Participant 2 claimed, aligns with the core principles of design thinking. This approach helps educators to understand the needs and perspectives of students, leading to the development of

resources that are more aligned with student needs (Henriksen, Richardson, & Mehta, 2017).

Participant 3's ability to explore multiple possibilities through design thinking is a testament to the methodology's capacity for fostering open-ended exploration of solutions. This flexible and explorative approach is essential for adapting to the complex and ever-changing landscape of education (Razzouk & Shute, 2012).

The creation of personalized and effective learning resources by Participant 4 through design thinking underscores the approach's potential for tailoring education to individual learner needs. This personalized approach is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in effective education (Schneider & Preckel, 2017).

Participant 5's experience with testing ideas and generating beneficial ideas is reflective of design thinking's iterative nature. This process allows educators to prototype and refine ideas continuously, enhancing the learning process by ensuring that the final resources are both innovative and effective.

Table 5

Participant 1 emphasized training should begin with understanding students' needs and perspectives, followed by brainstorming ideas, creating drafts, testing resources, and making necessary revisions. This process is reflective of iterative and empathetic approach central to design thinking in education (Ladachart, Khamlarsai, & Phothon, 2022).

Participant 2 believed that identifying the clear learning objectives, conducting research, and creating detailed plans are crucial for resource creation. This structured approach aligns with the principles of backward design, ensuring that resources are goal-oriented and effective (Wiggins & McTighe, 1999).

Participant 3 shared that training must cover various learning theories and focus on understanding learners' needs, which is essential for developing pedagogically sound resources and tailored to diverse learners (Hattie & Donoghue, 2021).

Participant 4 said key elements should include a needs assessment and a thorough understanding of the curriculum. Training should emphasize the alignment of resources with curricular goals while also addressing the specific needs of the student population (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

Participant 5 reiterated that training should also include brainstorming sessions, strategies for finding reliable resources, planning stages, and formulating modules that incorporate higher-order thinking skills questions to promote deep learning (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001).

In essence, participants' resource creation approach embodies the dual nature of Design Thinking, blending a mindset shift with a dynamic process (Carrol, 2014). This blend underpins the development of the learning resources, stimulating innovation, and enhancing teaching effectiveness.

Table 6

A learning module on resource creation should incorporate visual aids, simulations, and interactive elements to facilitate an immersive learning experience according to Participant 1. Visual aids can help conceptualize complex ideas, while simulations and interactive elements offer hands-on practice and engagement, aligning with the principles of multimedia learning (Mayer, 2020).

However, Participant 2 stated that techniques such as interactive activities, varied assessments, and the use of multimedia can significantly enhance the learning process. These methods cater to different learning styles and ensure that assessment is ongoing and multifaceted (Clark & Mayer, 2021).

Participant 3 believed that active learning strategies are crucial for resource creation module as they involve learners directly and encourage critical thinking and problem-solving. The techniques such as collaborative discussions, peer teaching, and reflective exercises can be particularly effective (Freeman et al., 2014).

Moreover, Participant 4 specified that incorporating problem-based learning, case studies, and project-based learning into resource creation modules can provide practical and contextual learning experiences. These methods encourage learners to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world problems (Bell, 2010).

Participant 5 said that a diverse range of activities and assessments can lead to a deeper understanding of the subject matter. By engaging students with various methods, they are more likely to internalize content and apply it effectively (Ambrose et al., 2010).

Therefore, the development and innovation of educational resources through design thinking offer a multifaceted approach that can significantly enhance teaching and learning experiences. From understanding and empathizing with students' needs to the practical application of brainstorming, testing, and revision processes, educators are empowered to create resources that are not only tailored to educational objectives but also resonate with diverse learner profiles. The integration of interactive elements, multimedia, and active learning strategies further underscores the shift towards a more dynamic, student-centered approach to education. Moreover, by incorporating methodologies such as problem-based learning and embedding higher-order thinking skills into resource creation, educators can foster deeper understanding and engagement among students. Collectively, these elements reflect a comprehensive model for teacher training in resource creation that is grounded in creativity, innovation, and a commitment to continuous improvement and adaptability in response to the evolving educational landscape.

Conclusions

The conclusion of this research study offers a nuanced synthesis of the design thinking process's significant implications within the realm of science education. It clarifies the challenges educators face, the iterative refinement essential for resource effectiveness, the manifold benefits of design thinking, and crucial recommendations for both training and resource creation techniques. This comprehensive analysis not only

mirrors the study's objectives but also projects a pathway for future educational practices and inquiries.

- **Educational Policy Implications:**

The identified challenges and the transformative potential of design thinking underscore the need for educational policies that foster innovation and adaptability. Policy changes should aim to provide educators with the flexibility to integrate design thinking principles, such as by enabling curriculum adjustments that accommodate new teaching methodologies and by supporting incorporation of technology in the classroom. Initiatives could include funding for design thinking training programs, incentives for schools that implement innovative teaching practices, and the development of platforms for sharing resources created through design thinking processes.

- **Connections to Educational Theories and Frameworks:**

The findings of this study align with constructivist learning theories, which posit that learners construct knowledge through experiences. Design thinking, with its emphasis on empathy and iterative learning, complements this by offering a structured yet flexible approach to creating educational experiences. Furthermore, SAMR model (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, Redefinition) and the TPACK framework (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge), which guide technology integration in education, are enriched by design thinking's focus on creative problem-solving and user-centered design. This suggests that these frameworks can serve as a theoretical foundation for integrating design thinking into educational resource development (Puentedura, 2006; Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

- **The Role of Collaboration:**

While this study focused on individual experiences, the potential for collaboration in the design thinking process cannot be overstated. Collaboration among educators, administrators, and students can significantly enhance the resource creation process, fostering a culture of shared innovation and continuous improvement. This collective approach can lead to more diverse and effective educational resources, aligning with the collaborative nature of design thinking itself.

- **Long-term Implications for Teacher Training:**

Long-term implications for teacher education programs are profound. Integrating design thinking principles into teacher training curricula can prepare future educators to meet the challenges of modern classrooms with agility and creativity. Such training should not only focus on the mechanics of design thinking but also emphasize its philosophical underpinnings—creativity, empathy, and a willingness to embrace failure as a step towards innovation.

- **The Impact of Technology:**

The importance of technology integration identified in this study highlights the role of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), and educational apps, in facilitating design thinking process. These technologies can provide immersive and personalized learning experiences, further

advancing the capabilities of educators to create resources that are engaging, effective, and tailored to students' needs.

This study highlights the crucial role of design thinking in the development of educational practices, specifically in the creation of the science learning resources. By advocating for policy changes, fostering collaborative environments, improving teacher training programs, and utilizing technology, the education sector can incorporate the principles of design thinking to better navigate the complexities of modern-day education. These findings not only address the immediate results of the research but also set the foundation for future studies on the vast potential of design thinking in education.

Recommendations

Based on the thematic analysis and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Refinement and Validation of the Learning Module:** The developed learning module, aiming to enhance teachers' abilities to employ Design Thinking in resource creation, represents a promising tool based on the study's findings. However, it's recommended that this module undergo further refinement and validation. The efficacy, acceptability, and utility of the module should be systematically assessed through pilot implementation, feedback collection, and subsequent iterations to improve its quality and relevance.
2. **Adopting Design Thinking in Resource Creation:** Encouraging the use of Design Thinking in the development of educational resources could foster creativity and innovation. It would also promote a learner-centric approach that could significantly improve learning materials engagement and effectiveness.
3. **Fostering Flexibility and Adaptability:** The educational context and learners' needs are continually evolving. As such, it is crucial to foster flexibility and adaptability in resource creation, allowing for the continual adjustments and refinement based on feedback and shifts in educational environment and needs.
4. **Nurturing Creativity and Innovation in Learners:** As the demand for these skills is high in modern workplace, educational resources should be designed to nurture creativity and innovation in learners. Nurturing could be achieved by incorporating problem-solving tasks and creative exercises in the learning materials.
5. **Emphasizing the Integration of Theory and Practice:** Incorporating experiential learning activities that integrate theory and practice could enhance the learning experience. These activities would also provide students with an opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts.
6. **Strengthening Alignment with 21st-Century Skills:** Educational resources should be designed to align with the 21st-Century Skills model, emphasizing critical thinking, creativity, problem-solving, and innovation. This alignment

- would ensure the relevance of learning materials in an increasingly globalized and technologically advanced society.
7. **Creating Supportive Environment for Innovation:** Schools and educational institutions should create environment that encourages and supports innovative practices in resource creation. This environment could include providing the training, resources, and time for teachers to experiment and innovate.
 8. **Embracing Technological Advancements:** Given rapid growth of technology and its integration into education, teachers should be encouraged and trained to leverage various technological tools in resource creation. This leverage could enhance the interactivity and engagement of learning materials.
 9. **Training and Professional Development:** Training programs for teachers should be developed to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to create effective learning resources. These programs should cover Design Thinking principles, modern pedagogical approaches, and the use of technology in education.
 10. **Collaboration and Sharing of Best Practices:** Encouraging collaboration among teachers and the sharing of best practices could enhance the quality and effectiveness of educational resources. Collaboration platforms could be established to facilitate this sharing and learning process.

It is strongly suggested that contemporary teaching techniques be employed in order to enhance educational materials, put learners' requirements first, and foster originality and inventiveness.

For future research in the area of resource creation and educational practices, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Evaluation of the Learning Module:** Future research should conduct a thorough evaluation of the learning module, focusing on its effectiveness in enhancing teachers' abilities to create innovative and engaging resources using Design Thinking. The assessment could be based on various factors such as teachers' feedback, students' engagement, learning outcomes, and usability and adaptability of the module in different educational contexts.
2. **Longitudinal Studies on Design Thinking Implementation:** In order to fully comprehend the effects of Design Thinking on educational resource development, further research could be conducted through longitudinal studies. These studies would allow for a deeper understanding of how this approach develops and changes in response to different contexts and needs over time.
3. **Comparative Studies across Different Education Systems:** Researchers could conduct comparative studies across different education systems or countries to gain insights into how cultural and systemic factors influence the application of Design Thinking and other innovative practices in resource creation.
4. **Impact of Technological Advancements:** Given the rapid technological advancements in the field of education, future studies could explore how emerging technologies, like artificial intelligence and augmented reality, can be integrated

into resource creation and how they influence student engagement and learning outcomes.

5. **Role of Teacher Training in Resource Creation:** Research could be conducted to understand the impact of teacher training programs on the quality of resources developed and the pedagogical practices employed. The effectiveness of different training approaches could also be evaluated.
6. **Student-Centric Approaches:** Further research could delve into the effectiveness of student-centric approaches in resource creation. Studies could assess the impact on student engagement, understanding, and learning outcomes when students are placed at the heart of resource design.
7. **Collaboration in Resource Creation:** Future research could explore the impact of collaboration among teachers, and possibly students, in resource creation. It would be valuable to understand how sharing ideas and practices influence the innovation and effectiveness of resources developed.
8. **Exploring Alternative Pedagogical Approaches:** Beyond Design Thinking, there are other pedagogical approaches, like Inquiry-Based Learning, that can influence resource creation. Future research could compare the effects of these different methodologies.

As the world rapidly evolves with new technologies and ways of learning, it is crucial for researchers to continuously explore and experiment with innovative methods for creating educational resources. By doing so, they can better understand how to cater to the dynamic needs of learners in today's fast-paced educational landscape. With a focus on efficiency and effectiveness, such research can lead to the development of more engaging and impactful learning materials, ultimately benefiting students and educators alike.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Adhering to the highest ethical standards was paramount in this research, guided by the principles outlined in the American Psychological Association's Publication Manual (2019). Central to our approach was informed consent, ensuring that all participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights as participants. Participation was voluntary, with participants informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained, with all identifiable information anonymized in the study's findings and data securely stored, accessible only to the research team. Moreover, the well-being and comfort of participants were prioritized throughout the research process, particularly during the data collection phase. This ethical framework not only safeguarded the participants but also reinforced the integrity and credibility of the research findings.

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